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**INNOVATIVE ECO-EFFICIENT PROCESSING AND REFINING
ROUTES FOR SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS FROM SILICON
INGOT AND WAFER MANUFACTURING FOR ACCELERATED
UTILISATION IN HIGH-END MARKETS**

The logo for CARUS, featuring a stylized green and white icon of a square with a smaller square inside, followed by the word "CARUS" in a bold, white, sans-serif font.

CCARUS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 958365

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01

ICARUS POSITIONNING IN THE PHOTOVOLTAIC INDUSTRY

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

ICARUS set out to transform upstream processing residues rich in high purity silicon and its embedded energy into valuable secondary raw materials. The project demonstrated modular and industrial scale processing solutions capable of recovering up to 95% of high value materials from silicon ingot and wafer manufacturing for photovoltaic applications. By applying eco-efficient processing, refining, and transformation of industrial silicon, graphite, and silica residues, ICARUS supports a more sustainable and resource efficient PV value chain.

Three industrial pilot lines were established to produce secondary silicon, silica and graphite raw materials. These included

- Pretreated and purified silicon, silica and graphite feedstocks
- A pyrometallurgical route that uses recovered materials to produce high purity silicon
- Granular silicon feedstock suitable for photovoltaic manufacturing

A fourth industrial pilot demonstrated the conversion of silicon rich process residues into green hydrogen, silica and silicates, enabling full value utilisation of this resource.

The secondary raw materials were validated in several high end and quality critical applications to assess both technical and economic feasibility, including solar grade silicon for photovoltaic wafers, aluminium silicon alloys, thermoelectric modules and generators, lithium-ion battery cells, silicon carbide powders and fine-grained graphite products.

02

STRONG PARTNERSHIP

THE ICARUS CONSORTIUM IS COMPOSED OF
17 PARTNERS FROM
8 DIFFERENT COUNTRIES

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SINTEF

SINTEF is the project coordinator. The organisation contributes comprehensive expertise in silicon crystallisation, wafer sawing, material refining, and the synthesis and characterisation of batteries and electrochemical cells. Within ICARUS, SINTEF also carried out several pilot campaigns for producing silicon metal from silicon and silica residues.

Northern Silicon

Northern Silicon has developed an innovative process for producing high-grade silicon from quartz and silicon metal for solar applications. Within ICARUS, the company demonstrated a three-step approach that includes pretreatment, melting and purification, which is well suited for recycling silica and silicon residues and supports future industrial scale up in Norway.

ReSiTec

ReSiTec specialises in the recovery and treatment of valuable materials from powders, liquids and suspensions. They bring long industrial experience in commercial silicon kerf recycling. Within ICARUS, they contributed to the collection and pretreatment of silicon, silica and graphite processing residues, enabling efficient downstream recovery and refining.

NorSun

NorSun produces high efficiency monocrystalline wafers for the global PV industry. In ICARUS, they supplied silicon, silica and graphite processing residues, developed separation techniques and tested recovered secondary silicon feedstock, contributing to the overall techno economic assessment.

ROSI

ROSI is a French technology company offering high value recycling solutions for PV manufacturing residues such as kerf loss, sawing slurries and silicon fines. In ICARUS, ROSI contributed to the controlled conditioning and purification of silicon residues and supported the recovery of PV grade secondary materials for reuse in PV-production.

bifa environmental institute

bifa is an applied environmental research and consulting institute with leading expertise in life cycle assessment and PV module end of life treatment. In ICARUS, bifa analysed the process sustainability and environmental benefits of high-quality material recovery routes.

Institut Polytechnique de Grenoble

Institut Polytechnique de Grenoble has long standing expertise in silicon purification and crystallisation research. Within ICARUS, their contribution focused on material development and scientific support aimed at improving the quality and processing performance of recovered silicon.

CEA LITEN

CEA LITEN is a major French research centre for solar energy technologies. Within ICARUS, they supported the validation of recovered silicon materials in photovoltaic applications and contributed to the evaluation of process and product performance.

LuxChemTech

LuxChemTech develops technologies for recovering strategic elements from high tech materials, including photovoltaic products. In ICARUS, they applied their hydrometallurgical expertise and specialised equipment to demonstrate pilot scale processing of silicon containing residues.

CIDETEC Energy Storage

CIDETEC develops advanced lithium-ion battery technologies and pathways for industrial uptake. In ICARUS, they validated recovered graphite and silicon in electrode formulations and cell testing and assessed their potential for battery applications.

University of Cyprus

The University of Cyprus worked on the development of thermoelectric silicide's and modules using silicon kerf instead of high-purity commercial silicon, demonstrating the potential of recovered materials in energy conversion devices.

Magneti Marelli Exhaust

Magneti Marelli Exhaust, now part of Marelli, develops high performance exhaust systems. In ICARUS, they evaluated recovered silicon materials for potential use in automotive thermal management and energy recovery solutions.

Gränges

Gränges develops advanced aluminium products with strong circularity objectives. In ICARUS, their research and innovation team tested recycled silicon kerf as an alloying material in industrial production lines to demonstrate feasibility in aluminium silicon alloys.

SGL Carbon

SGL Carbon is a global producer of specialty graphite materials. In ICARUS, they assessed refined graphite residues from the project and explored their integration into high value graphite products.

ChemConserve

ChemConserve commercialises recycling and critical raw material technologies. In ICARUS, they supported exploitation planning, business development and the development of commercialisation pathways for project innovations.

Benkei

Benkei is an innovation consultancy that supports strategic development, market analysis and exploitation planning. In ICARUS, they coordinated exploitation activities and helped translate project results into marketable solutions.

Fiven Norge

Fiven is a leading global producer of silicon carbide grains and powders. In ICARUS, they carried out pilot trials to convert recovered silica residues into silicon carbide fines suitable for semiconductor applications.

03

PHOTOVOLTAIC VALUE CHAIN AND THE ROLE OF SILICON

The photovoltaic value chain spans from raw materials to the manufacturing of PV-modules. It begins with high purity quartz, which is converted into metallurgical grade silicon through carbothermic reduction at about 2000 °C. This metallurgical grade silicon is essential for producing polysilicon for photovoltaic and semiconductor manufacturing, and it is also widely used in Al-Si alloys, silicones, battery materials and others. Its broad industrial relevance makes it a strategically important raw material.

To strengthen industrial resilience in Europe, it is important to increase both domestic production and the circular reuse of silicon resources. Large material streams from PV-manufacturing and end of life modules, such as recycled silicon, kerf-loss, crucibles, pot-scrap and graphite components, can be recovered and reintegrated into the PV-value chain. This supports sustainability, reduces import dependency and enhances competitiveness in a market currently dominated by fully integrated production outside Europe.

All downstream value chains depend on silicon, which is classified as a critical raw material. In the photovoltaic industry, each € created in the upstream segment generates about 2.7 € in downstream activities. Securing and improving the efficiency of this upstream value chain is therefore essential.

The process of converting silicon into wafers is very energy intensive, requiring about 80 MWh per tonne, and generates large processing residues. These primarily contain silicon, but also significant amounts of graphite and silica. The European project ICARUS is working to strengthen this process and support European growth in downstream value chains by transforming these upstream residues, rich in highly pure silicon and embedded energy, into valuable secondary raw materials.

Within ICARUS, four pilot lines were set up and used to demonstrate the corresponding processing routes:

- Pilot A – Collecting and pre-treating silicon, graphite and silica production processing residues (crushing, grinding and cleaning) to enable further valorisation
- Pilot B – Utilising silicon, graphite and silica secondary raw materials to produce metallurgical-grade silicon, replacing the use of virgin raw materials
- Pilot C – Conditioning, melting and purifying secondary silicon resources to improve material quality for PV applications
- Pilot D – Converting silicon-rich residues into valuable industrial products such as green hydrogen, silicates and silica

SECONDARY

RAW MATERIAL POTENTIAL

Crystalline silicon ingot and wafer production generates substantial volumes of secondary raw materials. Understanding how these volumes develop over time helps quantify both the challenge and the opportunity to retain these resources within the PV value chain or redirect them to other high-value applications.

The generation of silicon kerf depends on factors such as annual PV installations, regional production capacity, and wafering efficiency. The estimation of silica volumes is based on typical ingot pulling dimensions (e.g., M10 and G12), considering multi-batch furnace operation. Graphite generation can be projected using an industrial benchmark of approximately 100 tonnes per gigawatt of PV ingot production.

These projections confirm that large quantities of silicon, silica and graphite will continue to arise as by-products of PV ingot and wafer manufacturing. Valorising these secondary raw materials reduces demand for virgin resources, supports resource efficiency, and lowers overall environmental impacts.

SILICON KERF VOLUME ESTIMATION FROM SILICON INGOT AND WAFER MANUFACTURING PROCESS.

SILICA (LEFT) AND GRAPHITE (RIGHT) WASTE VOLUME ESTIMATION FROM SILICON INGOT AND WAFER MANUFACTURING PROCESS.

PILOT A — RESITEC UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY IN SILICON INGOT AND WAFER MANUFACTURING

Material streams for recovery

Silicon kerf-loss generated from diamond wire wafering of silicon Czochralski ingots in the photovoltaic industry represents a high-volume silicon source of more than 300 000 tonnes per year. ReSiTec has developed industrial processes for recovering, purifying and processing silicon kerf into a dry, fine silicon powder that can potentially be used as an anode material in lithium-ion batteries and thermoelectric modules.

Silica crucible and graphite residues were also processed in dedicated pilot lines designed for handling these material streams.

Pilot-scale demonstrations

Silicon kerf-loss processing:

- Continuous drying with <1 wt% moisture
- Industrial pretreatment and post-processing steps producing deagglomerated, clean silicon powder
- Pilot capacity: 100-300 kg/h
- >95% recovery of usable silicon
- Low carbon footprint compared with virgin silicon

The developed process is highly energy-efficient, resulting in a significantly reduced carbon footprint for silicon powder produced from kerf recycling. Electrochemical testing of ReSiTec's recycled silicon demonstrated performance comparable to commercial nano-silicon, highlighting its potential as a cost-efficient, low-carbon anode material for Li-ion batteries. In addition, the material has been successfully tested in thermoelectric modules, demonstrating promising performance.

Silicon powder material produced in pilot A and typical size distributions for different sources of silicon kerf

Process flow sheet for the pilot-line for processing of silica crucible- and graphite waste materials

Silica crucible and graphite waste materials:

A dedicated pilot line was developed for the treatment of silica crucible and graphite residues from silicon Czochralski crystallisation furnaces.

Left: incoming silica crucible waste materials; Right: silica crucible waste materials after processing in pilot line at ReSiTec

Silica crucible residues processed in ReSiTec's pilot line have been successfully utilised for the production of both silicon carbide and metallurgical-grade silicon. The results confirm the feasibility of obtaining high-purity silicon carbide and quality metallurgical-grade silicon from these recycled materials.

Across all tested waste streams, including silicon kerf-loss from wafer sawing, graphite from crystallisation furnaces, and silica from melting containers, recovery rates above 95 % were achieved, highlighting the high efficiency and circularity of the developed process route.

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PILOT B — NORTHERN SILICON PRODUCING METALLURGICAL- GRADE SILICON FROM SECONDARY RESOURCES

This pilot focuses on utilising silicon kerf-loss, graphite, and quartz crucible materials using Northern Silicon's process technology to produce metallurgical-grade silicon suitable for reuse in photovoltaic manufacturing.

Two key challenges have been identified:

- Solar-grade silicon requires extremely high purity to at least 99.9999% purity.
- Silicon kerf-loss contains dopants such as phosphorus and boron, which are difficult and costly to remove and must be reduced to below 0.2 ppm each.

The process begins with the collection and pretreatment of silicon kerf-loss, graphite and silica crucible residues, involving washing, drying, grinding, and quality characterization. In the next step, the pretreated materials are agglomerated into briquettes with stoichiometric composition for carbothermic reduction. These briquettes, together with virgin and recycled materials, are then reduced in a submerged arc furnace to produce metallurgical-grade silicon. Finally, the produced silicon undergoes purity analysis to determine its quality and composition.

CARBOTHERMIC REDUCTION OF SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS
FOR SILICON PRODUCTION

A briquetting unit with a capacity of 200 kg/h, along with a drying cabinet for green briquettes, has been successfully commissioned. The unit produces briquettes with excellent mechanical strength. Two types of briquettes were developed: silicon-kerf-based briquettes and self-reducing briquettes formulated from silica crucible residues and carbon black. In total, 1.5 tonnes of briquettes were produced for the submerged arc furnace pilot campaigns.

THE BRIQUETTING MACHINE AND THE DRYING CABINET.

Two experimental campaigns, including four pilot trials, were conducted using a 250 t/y submerged arc furnace to convert silicon kerf briquettes, self-reducing silica briquettes, and silica lumps into metallurgical-grade silicon. Each campaign lasted three days and nights, focusing on furnace preheating, operation, charge preparation, and tapping activities.

MAIN ACTIVITIES IN SAF OPERATION FOR SILICON PRODUCTION.

PURITY ANALYSIS OF THE PRODUCED SILICON.

Thanks to the high purity of the silicon produced from recycled materials, it can directly enter the metallurgical and chemical routes (Siemens process) for further refinement into solar-grade and electronic-grade polysilicon.

PROCESS FLOW FOR UPGRADING MG-SI TO HIGH-PURITY SILICON THROUGH SUCCESSIVE REFINING AND CRYSTALLIZATION STEPS.

1. Briquetting and material preparation

- The briquetting mix and method developed at Northern Silicon (NOSI) work effectively for both kerf and crucible quartz, contributing to an energy-efficient process for metallurgical-grade silicon production.
- Strong agglomerates suitable for SAF operation can be produced using carbon black, milled pot scrap, sugar, and water, followed by briquetting and heat treatment. Kerf briquettes can also be made using only kerf, sugar, and water.

2. Performance of secondary raw materials

- Graphite residues from crystallisation furnaces are not sufficiently reactive to replace carbon black as a reducing agent. Additional drawbacks include high ash variability, labour-intensive processing, and limited availability.
- Silica from crucibles can replace virgin material for standard-grade silicon production, though its impurity content restricts its use in high-purity applications.
- Silicon kerf shows strong potential as a feedstock for silicon wafer production, though further testing is needed.

3. Silicon yield improvement

- Self-reducing briquettes with a C/SiO₂ molar ratio near 3 enable efficient silicon production when carbon coverage is properly optimised.
- Adding silica pot-scrap lumps increases silicon yield, as their reduction is highly energy-efficient, comparable to or better than virgin quartz.
- Silicon yield also improves with silicon kerf briquettes, since this material is already in a reduced state.

70% Recycled

Up to 70% of the raw materials used in silicon production come from recycled sources, reducing reliance on virgin inputs.

PILOT C – ROSI CONTROLLED SILICON CONDITIONING FOR INDUSTRIAL UPTAKE

At ROSI, a combined system for powder feeding, melting, solidification, and granulation has been developed and commissioned to recycle silicon kerf into high-purity silicon. The powder feeding unit has a capacity of 500 t/year, while the melting and granulation line operates at 50 t/year.

The granulation unit enables the continuous production of liquid silicon droplets through a silicon-specific drip-nozzle design. These droplets are crystallised on a cooled rotating soleplate, producing uniform granules that are continuously collected. The system, currently dedicated to 50 t/year, has been designed for full flexibility, allowing process optimisation and scale-up to several hundred tons of silicon powder per year.

Using this process, recycled silicon has been produced from kerf at a flow rate of 1 kg/h, achieving 4N purity and significantly reduced carbon and oxygen contents (approximately 110 ppm C and 15 ppm O). Ongoing process improvements target 6N purity, enabling direct use in solar applications such as wafers, solar cells, as well as in alloys and composites.

The final products can be conditioned as 4-10 mm granules, square ingots, or rods, offering versatile formats for downstream industrial use.

Metallic impurities concentrations (GDMS)

Si-granules purity = 99,989% wt. (≈4N)

PILOT D – LUXCHEMTECH CONVERTING SILICON WASTE INTO VALUABLE MATERIALS

At LuxChemtech, a chemical demonstrator with a capacity of approximately 90 t/year has been successfully commissioned to convert silicon kerf-loss and other silicon-containing residues into valuable products. The process produces high-quality silica, various grades of water glass solutions, and green hydrogen, all suitable for a wide range of industrial applications.

In addition to silicon kerf-loss, alternative side streams from the photovoltaic and semiconductor industries are also considered valuable feedstock materials. For instance, around 11 grams of silver, worth roughly €17, can be recovered from just one kilogram of photovoltaic cell scrap, providing an additional economic incentive and further improving the overall sustainability of the process.

Overview about using PV scrap for generating H₂ and waterglass

The recycling of silicon waste into valuable materials can be extended far beyond kerf recycling. The LuxChemtech technology also shows strong potential for processing silicon recovered from end-of-life photovoltaic modules and other industrial waste sources. Additional side streams, such as silicon contaminated with corundum or graphite, have also been successfully tested with the aim of isolating and recovering these valuable materials, further broadening the circular use of silicon-based materials.

CIRCULAR SOLUTIONS – ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

Circular processing of silicon offers a powerful opportunity to cut emissions and reduce resource demand in the ICARUS value chain. By turning Si-kerf residues into high-quality secondary silicon, the project shows how innovative recycling routes can outperform conventional production across multiple environmental impact categories.

PILOT

A

Producing silicon from recycled Si-kerf residues can reduce greenhouse gas emissions by more than tenfold compared to conventional production. Processing Si-kerf into secondary dry silicon with less than 1% moisture performs far better in terms of climate impact than the traditional production of metallurgical-grade silicon.

In these secondary silicon routes, most emissions come from electricity use and, to a smaller extent, transport. For primary silicon, emissions are mainly driven by the electricity mix - very high in China due to coal-based power, and lower in Europe, where direct process emissions are the main source.

Secondary dry silicon achieves lower ecology indices, indicating better performance across all environmental impact categories compared to primary silicon. From an environmental standpoint, producing secondary dry silicon with less than 1% moisture is therefore far more sustainable than conventional metallurgical-grade silicon production in both Europe and China.

This advantage stems mainly from the ICARUS process's much lower energy and material demands - using over eight times less electricity than traditional routes, and from the fact that it does not rely on fossil fuels for heat generation.

Secondary silicon production results in significantly lower greenhouse gas emissions (mainly fossil CO₂) compared to conventional solar-grade silicon. Processing Si-kerf waste into secondary silicon with 6N+/8N purity performs much better in terms of climate impact than traditional production routes in both Europe and China.

In the secondary silicon scenarios, emissions mainly arise from electricity use and, to a smaller extent, transport. For primary solar-grade silicon, most emissions are linked to electricity supply and to the energy-intensive production of metallurgical-grade silicon as a pre-product.

Secondary silicon achieves lower ecology indices and thus performs better across all environmental impact categories compared to primary silicon. Producing secondary silicon with 6N+/8N purity is therefore far more sustainable than conventional solar-grade silicon production in both Europe and China.

This improvement is mainly due to the ICARUS processes, which require between five and fifty times less electricity and no thermal energy. In addition, the use of Si-kerf-loss as feedstock drastically reduces the need for raw materials compared to traditional primary production.

The Si-kerf-loss to material/energy scenario results in a much lower climate impact than the conventional production pathway. Turning Si-kerf waste into electricity, heat, and water glass leads to considerably fewer greenhouse gas emissions than producing these materials and energy streams through standard processes.

In the ICARUS scenario, 86% of total emissions come from the production of water glass and the generation of electricity and heat, while 14% is linked to the collection and cleaning of the Si-kerf waste.

In the conventional scenario, the picture is reversed: 85% of emissions are associated with the production of sodium silicate, whereas electricity and heat generation account for only 15% of the total.

The Si-kerf-loss to material/energy scenario shows consistently lower environmental impacts across all categories when compared with the conventional production route. Converting Si-kerf waste into electricity, heat, and water glass therefore offers a more sustainable alternative to producing the same outputs through traditional processes.

Across both scenarios, the main drivers of environmental impact are climate change, use of fossil resources, and use of mineral and metal resources. These categories make up about 55% of the total impact in the Si-kerf waste to material/energy scenario and 62% in the conventional scenario.

In the Si-kerf waste to material/energy pathway, water use and freshwater eutrophication also play a notable role, each contributing around 11% to the overall impact. In the conventional production route, particulate matter formation is a more significant contributor, accounting for roughly 9% of the total.

IMPRINT

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